

Development of Newer Methodologies in Organic Synthesis†

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Synthesis of biologically (or medicinally) important natural products (or non-naturally occurring compounds) has been an attractive area of considerable research interest. These synthetic ventures comprise of the uses of reagents, reactions and synthons (R.R.S.) as tools to reach the target molecules. In other words these tools (R.R.S.) act as building blocks towards the targets. Development of these tools is termed as methodology developments. While developing these methodologies the selectivity aspect, viz. regio, chemo, stereo (diastereo) and more recently enantioselectivities becomes of prime concern. Alongwith these aspects if there is a possibility of developing methodologies at low cost and avoiding potentially hazardous reagents it is even better.

For the past ten years we have been involved in developing methodologies possibly meeting the above mentioned criteria.

One of the first reagents employed by us is a combination of zinc and chlorotrimethylsilane¹. Since epoxides react with ClSiMe_3 only at 100° to give ring-opened products, it became of interest to us to examine the behaviour of Zn-ClSiMe_3 towards epoxides. We expected zinc to play an important role in these reactions. It was found by us² that Zn-ClSiMe_3 reacted with a variety of epoxides to give alcohols within 5 min at 0° to room temperature. Further, it is important to mention here that less substituted alcohol was found to be major product. A few examples are shown below :

Further exploration of the potential of Zn-ClSiMe_3 reagent system led³ to the following regio-specific reductions of 2,3-epoxyacetals which eventually could be converted into 1,2-diones.

Interestingly 2,3-epoxyacetals upon reduction with LiAlH_4 gave 3-hydroxyacetals as exclusive products which, in turn, were converted into 1,3-diones.

Several examples of these sequences of reactions speak of the generality of the process and access to 1,2- and 1,3-diones which are useful intermediates in organic synthesis.

Using this Zn-ClSiMe_3 combination conjugated ene-diones were easily reduced⁴ to 1,4-diketones under mild conditions.

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Another reagent system, NaI-BF₃·Et₂O, was utilised by us in chemoselective conversions of alcohols into iodides, sulphoxides into sulphides⁶, selective deprotection of ethers⁶, reduction of conjugated ene-diones into 1,4-diketones⁴ and more recently in the conversion of tetrahydropyranylated ethers into iodides⁷. These transformations are schematically shown below with the help of one example each.

N-Iodosuccinimide (NIS), an important reagent, is an excellent source of I⁺. However, its storage requires precautions as this reagent is heat and light sensitive. Literature procedure⁸ to prepare NIS involves the following sets of reactions.

Use of silver oxide being rather restricted due to its high cost, we sought another approach towards the synthesis of NIS. It was found by us⁹ that *N*-chlorosuccinimide, a stable compound, upon treatment with NaI in acetone immediately formed NIS in almost quantitative yield. The precipitated NaCl could be filtered off and the solvent evaporated to give almost pure NIS. This procedure allowed us to prepare NIS prior to its use thus avoiding its storage problem. Further, if Cl⁻ did not interfere in the reactions NaCl need not be filtered off. The following two types of transformations were carried out using freshly prepared NIS.

In the latter case NaCl was not filtered off. This method of NIS preparation has received considerable attention by other chemists¹⁰.

Tetrakis(triphenyl phosphine)palladium(0) [Pd(PPh₃)₄] has been used by Suzuki *et al.* as a reagent for the isomerisation of vinyl epoxides¹¹ and 2,3-epoxyketones¹² into α,β -unsaturated ketones (or dienols) and 1,3-diketones respectively. Mechanistic details as suggested by Suzuki *et al.* prompted us to investigate the potential of epoxide isomerisations of 2,3-epoxy-alcohols and α -nitroepoxides.

Isomerisation of the epoxy-alcohols gave¹³ a mixture of two keto-alcohols which arise by the attack of Pd(0) on either of the two carbons of the

epoxide. A variety of examples, studied by us, clearly indicated that the nature of R and Ar played important roles in directing the attack of Pd(0) and consequently on the hydroxy-ketones.

The second reaction was still more interesting as it required the use of Et₃N for the completion of the reaction. The α-nitroepoxide first underwent isomerisation to α-nitro-ketones which under the reaction conditions further underwent some type of Nef reaction to give the α-diketones¹⁴.

Conversion of α-nitroepoxides to α-diketones was also carried out by us¹⁵ in a slightly different manner, but more efficiently, as shown below.

Attack of the nucleophile (DMSO in this case) followed by the loss of NO₂ group is an important aspect of these reactions. Recently, we have studied¹⁶ such ring opening reactions more in depth and found that a variety of nucleophiles reacted with α-nitroepoxides to give α-substituted-ketones. These reactions suggest that α-nitroepoxides are α-keto carbocation equivalent.

Ritter reaction¹⁷ has been one of the simplest reactions which allows the introduction of nitrogen in a compound that could give a carbocation. In our efforts to synthesise pharmacologically active

2H-1,3-benzothiazines we made¹⁸ use of this reaction as shown below.

The intermediate A as shown above further encouraged us to look if Pummerer rearrangement could be utilised in these reactions. When a sulfoxide is treated with a nitrile, trifluoroacetic anhydride and trifluoroacetic acid the corresponding amides were obtained¹⁹. This is the first example of Ritter reaction on Pummerer intermediate.

The intermediate (B), instead of undergoing cyclisation, underwent nucleophilic attack by $\ominus\text{OCOCF}_3$ to give (C) which eventually gave the amide.

In continuation to explore the potential of Ritter reactions we have found that cyclopropyl ketones and cyclopropyl alcohols undergo²⁰ ring-opening by nitriles to give N-acyl keto and N-acyl homoallyl amines respectively.

Recently Corey and Estreicher²¹ reported an interesting NO₂ group containing synthon (D) (shown below) which was utilised as an excellent dienophile. In order to make use of this in other reactions, we became interested in synthesising this compound. The reported procedure for its preparation is as follows.

The non-availability of 90% H₂O₂ as well as the potential hazard in its use made us to look for an alternate synthesis of (D). A new procedure developed by us⁹ is shown below.

In the process we have synthesised a new synthon (E). Likewise another such type of synthon (F) has also been recently synthesised by us. These important compounds (E) and (F) have been found¹⁶ to undergo a variety of reactions to yield highly functionalised intermediates.

α -Hydroxy- β,γ -unsaturated esters (G) have been recognised by us as excellent synthons. One of the easiest ways to synthesise these has been developed²⁸ as follows.

Its utility in the preparation of oxacycles (H) is shown above.

In summary, we have developed a variety of methodologies, viz. R.R.S. (reagents, reactions and synthons) which are useful in organic synthesis.

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